

ON PRODUCTS AND SHIFTED PRODUCTS OF RESIDUES MODULO P

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Abstract

It is shown that if p is a prime and $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}$ are large subsets of \mathbb{Z}_p , then the equation $ab + 1 = cd$, $a \in \mathcal{A}$, $b \in \mathcal{B}$, $c \in \mathcal{C}$, $d \in \mathcal{D}$ can be solved.

– Dedicated to Mel Nathanson on the occasion of his 60th birthday

1. Introduction

Throughout this paper we will use the notation $e(\alpha) = e^{2\pi i\alpha}$. In [2] I proved that if p is a prime and $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}$ are “large” subsets of \mathbb{Z}_p , then the equation

$$(1) \quad a + b = cd, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}$$

can be solved:

Theorem A. *If p is a prime, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$, and the number of solutions of (1) is denoted by N , then we have*

$$(2) \quad \left| N - \frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|}{p} \right| \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{1/2}.$$

Corollary A. *If p is a prime, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$, and*

$$(3) \quad |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| > p^3,$$

then (1) can be solved.

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I also showed that Corollary A and thus also the theorem is the best possible apart from the constant factor in (3), resp. (2), and that these results cannot be extended to composite moduli.

These results generalize several earlier results and also have some new interesting consequences. Among others, they cover the solvability of:

$$(i) \quad \chi(a + b) = e\left(\frac{n}{d}\right), \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}$$

where χ is a (multiplicative) character modulo p of order d , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, and \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} are “large” subsets of \mathbb{Z}_p ;

(ii) both equations

$$\left(\frac{a + b}{p}\right) = +1, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}$$

and

$$\left(\frac{a' + b'}{p}\right) = -1, \quad a' \in \mathcal{A}, b' \in \mathcal{B}$$

where $\left(\frac{n}{p}\right)$ is the Legendre symbol modulo p ;

(iii) $a + b = x^k$, $a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_p, x \neq 0$ where $k \in \mathbb{N}$; in particular,

$$x^m + y^n \equiv z^k \pmod{p}, \quad xyz \neq 0$$

(whose $m = n = k$ special case is the Fermat congruence

$$x^n + y^n \equiv z^n \pmod{p}, \quad xyz \neq 0).$$

Some of these equations also have an interesting multiplicative analog studied earlier in which the sums $a + b$ are replaced by shifted products $ab + 1$. In particular, Vinogradov [3] estimated sums

$$(4) \quad \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \left(\frac{ab + 1}{p}\right)$$

and Gyarmati [1] studied the solvability of

$$ab + 1 = x^k, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_p.$$

In this paper our goal is to show that these problems and results can be generalized by proving the multiplicative analog of Theorem A:

Theorem 1. *If p is a prime, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$, and the number of solutions of the equation*

$$(5) \quad ab + 1 = cd, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}$$

is denoted by N , then we have

$$(6) \quad \left| N - \frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|}{p} \right| \leq 9(|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{1/2} + 3p^2.$$

Corollary 1. *If p is a prime, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$ and*

$$(7) \quad |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| > 100p^3,$$

then (5) can be solved.

Note that Corollary 1 and thus also Theorem 1 is the best possible apart from the constant factor in (7), resp. (6). Indeed, if p is a prime of form $p = 4k - 1$, and we take $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{B} = \left\{ r : r \in \mathbb{Z}_p, \left(\frac{r}{p}\right) = +1 \right\}$ (here and in what follows we do not distinguish between integers and residue classes represented by them) where $\left(\frac{r}{p}\right)$ denotes the Legendre symbol, $\mathcal{C} = \mathbb{Z}_p$ and $\mathcal{D} = \{0\}$, then we have

$$|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| = \left(\frac{1}{4} + o(1)\right) p^3,$$

however, (5) has no solution.

First in Section 2 we will prove several consequences of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1, and the proofs of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1 will be presented in Section 3.

2. Consequences

Corollary 2. *If p is a prime number, χ is a (multiplicative) character modulo p of order d , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$ and*

$$(8) \quad |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}| > 100d^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-2} p,$$

then there are $a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}$ with

$$(9) \quad \chi(ab + 1) = e\left(\frac{n}{d}\right).$$

Proof. Writing $\mathcal{C} = \{u : u \in \mathbb{Z}_p, \chi(u) = 1\}$ and $\mathcal{D} = \{v : v \in \mathbb{Z}_p, \chi(v) = e\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)\}$, we have

$$|\mathcal{C}| = |\mathcal{D}| = \frac{p-1}{d}$$

so that, by (8),

$$|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| > 100d^2 \frac{p^3}{(p-1)^2} \frac{(p-1)^2}{d^2} = 100p^3.$$

Thus by Corollary 1, (5) can be solved. If a, b, c, d satisfy (5) then we have

$$\chi(ab + 1) = \chi(cd) = \chi(c)\chi(d) = 1 \cdot e\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) = e\left(\frac{n}{d}\right)$$

so that (9) holds and this completes the proof of Corollary 2. □

In particular, if $\chi(n) = \left(\frac{n}{p}\right)$ (for $(n, p) = 1$) is the Legendre symbol in Corollary 2 so that $d = 2$, then we get the following result.

Corollary 3. *If p is an odd prime, $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B} \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$ and*

$$(10) \quad |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}| > 400 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-2} p$$

then there are $a, a' \in \mathcal{A}, b, b' \in \mathcal{B}$ with

$$\left(\frac{ab + 1}{p}\right) = +1, \quad \left(\frac{a'b' + 1}{p}\right) = -1$$

Apart from the constant factor in (10), this would also follow from Vinogradov’s estimate for the sum (4).

The following is a variant of a special case of Gyarmati’s Theorem 10. a) in [1].

Corollary 4. *If p is a prime, $k \in \mathbb{N}, A, B \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$ and, writing $D = (k, p - 1)$, we have*

$$(11) \quad |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}| > 100D^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-2} p,$$

then the equation

$$(12) \quad ab + 1 = x^k, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, x \in \mathbb{Z}_p, x \neq 0$$

can be solved.

Proof. Writing $\mathcal{E} = \{x^k : x \in \mathbb{Z}_p, x \neq 0\}$, clearly we have

$$|\mathcal{E}| = \frac{p - 1}{D}.$$

Thus taking $\mathcal{C} = \mathcal{D} = \mathcal{E}$, by (11) we have

$$|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| = |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}| \left(\frac{p - 1}{D}\right)^2 > 100p^3$$

so that by Corollary 1, (5) can be solved. For a, b, c, d satisfying (5) we have

$$ab + 1 = cd \in \mathcal{CD} = \mathcal{E} \cdot \mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}$$

which proves the solvability of (12). □

3. Proofs of Theorem 1 and Corollary 1

Proof of Theorem 1. Write

$$N_1 = |\{(a, b, c, d) : ab + 1 = cd \neq 0, a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}\}|$$

and

$$N_2 = |\{(a, b, c, d) : ab + 1 = cd = 0, a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}\}|$$

so that

$$(13) \quad N = N_1 + N_2.$$

Then, denoting the principal character modulo p by χ_0 , we have

$$(14) \quad \begin{aligned} N_1 &= \frac{1}{p-1} \sum_{\chi} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi(ab+1) \bar{\chi}(cd) = \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} \left(\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi_0((ab+1)cd) \right) + \\ &\quad + \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi(ab+1) \bar{\chi}(cd) = \\ &= \frac{1}{p-1} (N_3 + N_4) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$(15) \quad \begin{aligned} N_3 &= \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi_0((ab+1)cd) = \\ &= |\{(a, b, c, d) : a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}\}| - \\ &\quad - |\{(a, b, c, d) : (ab+1)cd = 0, a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}\}| = \\ &= |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| - N_5 \end{aligned}$$

with

$$N_5 = |\{(a, b, c, d) : (ab+1)cd = 0, a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}\}|$$

and

$$N_4 = \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \left(\sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \chi(ab+1) \right) \left(\sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \bar{\chi}(cd) \right).$$

It remains to estimate N_2 , N_4 and N_5 . First we have consider N_2 . In the definition of N_2 we have

$$(16) \quad ab + 1 = cd = 0, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}$$

Here $a \in \mathcal{A}$ can be chosen in at most $|\mathcal{A}|$ ways, and it determines b uniquely. Moreover, either we have $c = 0$ and then d can be chosen in $|\mathcal{D}|$ ways, or $d = 0$ and then c can be chosen in $|\mathcal{C}|$ ways. It follows that the number of solutions of (16), i. e., N_2 is

$$(17) \quad N_2 = |N_2| \leq |\mathcal{A}| (|\mathcal{C}| + |\mathcal{D}|) \leq 2p^2.$$

Now consider N_5 , i.e., the number of solutions of

$$(ab + 1)cd = 0, \quad a \in \mathcal{A}, b \in \mathcal{B}, c \in \mathcal{C}, d \in \mathcal{D}.$$

This holds if and only if one of

$$(18) \quad ab + 1 = 0,$$

$$(19) \quad c = 0,$$

$$(20) \quad d = 0$$

holds. In case (18), a can be chosen in at most $|\mathcal{A}|$ ways, it determines b uniquely, and c, d can be chosen in $|\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|$ ways. In case (19), a, b, d can be chosen in $|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{D}|$ ways, while in case (20), a, b, c can be chosen in $|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}|$ ways. It follows that

$$(21) \quad \begin{aligned} N_5 = |N_5| &\leq |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| + |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{D}| + |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}| \leq \\ &\leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|) \left((|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} + (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} + (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}|)^{1/2} \right) \leq \\ &\leq 3 (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{3/2}. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we have

$$(22) \quad |N_4| \leq \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \chi(ab + 1) \right| \left| \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \chi(c) \right| \left| \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi(d) \right|.$$

By Theorem 7 of Gyarmati in [1] for $\chi \neq \chi_0$ we have

$$\left| \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{b \in \mathcal{B}} \chi(ab + 1) \right| \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1).$$

(Gyarmati claimed this without the last term $+1$ but she overlooked the contribution of the terms with $b = 0$, and this additional term $+1$ is needed to cover their contribution.) Thus it follows from (22) that

$$|N_4| \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1) \sum_{\chi \neq \chi_0} \left| \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \chi(c) \right| \left| \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi(d) \right|$$

whence, by the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality,

$$(23) \quad |N_4| \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1) \left(\sum_x \left| \sum_{c \in \mathcal{C}} \chi(c) \right|^2 \right)^{1/2} \left(\sum_x \left| \sum_{d \in \mathcal{D}} \chi(d) \right|^2 \right)^{1/2}.$$

By a well-known identity, for any complex numbers z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{p-1} we have

$$\sum_x \left| \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} z_n \chi(n) \right|^2 = (p-1) \sum_{n=1}^{p-1} |z_n|^2.$$

Thus we obtain from (23) that

$$(24) \quad |N_4| \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1) ((p-1)|\mathcal{C}|)^{1/2} ((p-1)|\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} = (p-1) (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1).$$

It follows from (13), (14), (15), (17), (21) and (24) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| N - \frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|}{p} \right| = \\ & = \left| \frac{1}{p-1} (((|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| - N_5) + N_4) + N_2) - \frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|}{p} \right| \leq \\ & \leq |\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}| \left| \frac{1}{p-1} - \frac{1}{p} \right| + \frac{1}{p-1} (|N_5| + |N_4|) + |N_2| \leq \\ & \leq (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} \frac{(|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2}}{(p-1)p} + \\ & + 3 \frac{p}{p-1} (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{1/2} + (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} (p^{1/2} + 1) + \\ & + 2p^2 \leq 9 (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{1/2} + 3p^2 \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof of the theorem. □

Proof of Corollary 1. By Theorem 1, it follows from (7) that

$$\begin{aligned} N & \geq \frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|}{p} - 9 (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} p^{1/2} - 3p^2 = \\ & = (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} \left(\frac{|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|^{1/2}}{p} - 9p^{1/2} \right) - 3p^2 > \\ & > (|\mathcal{A}||\mathcal{B}||\mathcal{C}||\mathcal{D}|)^{1/2} (10p^{1/2} - 9p^{1/2}) - 3p^2 > \\ & > 10p^{3/2} \cdot p^{1/2} - 3p^2 = 7p^2 > 0 \end{aligned}$$

whence the result follows. □

4. A Generalization of the Problem

Both Theorem A and Theorem 1 are results of the following type: for a certain polynomial $F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{Z}[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ there is a number $c = c(F)$ such that if p is a prime, $A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n \subset \mathbb{Z}_p$, and $|A_1| |A_2| \cdots |A_n| > cp^{n-1}$, then the equation

$$F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = 0, \quad x_1 \in A_1, x_2 \in A_2, \dots, x_n \in A_n$$

can be solved. Indeed, in both cases we have $n = 4$; in Theorem A we have $F(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = x_1 + x_2 - x_3 x_4$, while in Theorem 1, $F(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = x_1 x_2 - x_3 x_4 + 1$. One might like to try to describe all the polynomials F with this property. However, this problem is, probably, too difficult; thus, there are easier problems to be studied first. In particular, the following questions can be asked: is it true that if $F(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$ is a polynomial of this type, then we must have $n \geq 4$? For $n = 4$, what are the other “good” polynomials F ? Again, the latter question seems to be difficult as the following nontrivial negative examples indicate:

Example 1 If $F(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = x_1 x_2 - x_3 x_4$, p is a prime,

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{B} = \mathcal{C} = \left\{ n : 0 < n < p, \binom{n}{p} = 1 \right\}$$

and

$$\mathcal{D} = \left\{ n : 0 < n < p, \binom{n}{p} = -1 \right\},$$

then we have

$$(25) \quad |\mathcal{A}| |\mathcal{B}| |\mathcal{C}| |\mathcal{D}| = \left(\frac{1}{16} + o(1) \right) p^4;$$

however,

$$(26) \quad F(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = 0, \quad x_1 \in \mathcal{A}, \quad x_2 \in \mathcal{B}, \quad x_3 \in \mathcal{C}, \quad x_4 \in \mathcal{D}$$

cannot be solved.

Example 2 If $F(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) = (x_1 + x_2)^2 + (x_3 + x_4)^2$, p is a prime of form $4k - 1$, and $\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{B} = \mathcal{C} = \mathcal{D} = \{n : 0 < n < p/2\}$, then again (25) holds, but (26) cannot be solved.

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